

Thiodiazines. Part VII. Condensation of Ethyl Chloroacetate with Thiosemicarbazides.

BY PRAFULLA KUMAR BOSE AND BIRENDRA KUMAR NANDI.

Some derivatives of 5-hydroxythiodiazines have previously been obtained by Bose (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 148) and by Guha and Roy-Choudhury (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 153) who showed that condensation of substances of the type $R'C(SH) = N \cdot NH_2$ (where $R' = S\text{-alkyl}$ or $PhNH \cdot NH-$) with α -halogenated aliphatic esters in presence of suitable condensing agents led to the formation of hydroxythiodiazines.* This reaction has now been extended to thiosemicarbazide and 4-substituted thiosemicarbazides, which are structurally analogous to those substances that have already been employed for the synthesis of 1:3:4-thiodiazines.

The reaction between ethyl chloroacetate (or the acid) and thiosemicarbazides is not as energetic as that between a thiosemicarbazide and an halogenated ketone, and the yield, though good, is not quantitative. Condensing agents like pyridine or alcoholic alkali appear to influence the velocity of the reaction as also the yield, but not to a considerable extent. The reactions have been carried out mainly in absence of any condensing agent, as this procedure gave a cleaner product.

The high-melting crystalline products of condensation may be represented by the general formula (I) which agrees with the observed properties. They dissolve in warm aqueous alkalis as also in acids, and yield monoacetyl derivatives on acetylation in the usual manner. They could not be desulphurised by freshly prepared yellow mercuric oxide or alkaline lead oxide—a test which is employed for the orientation of a sulphur atom in heterocyclic compounds. It was further concluded, on account of the indifference of the compounds towards ketones and aldehydes, that they do not carry any

* There appears to be some anomaly regarding the thiodiazine constitution assigned to the compound (XXVI) of Guha and Roy-Choudhury (*ibid.*, p. 154). The benzylidene derivative of this compound should be expected to be identical with their compound (XXIX) but they are reported to have different properties.

hydrazino-group, as might be expected if the products had the thiazole constitution (II), which is isomeric with (I) (*cf.* Besthorn, *Ber.*, 1910, 45, 1523).

(I)

(II)

The monoacetyl derivatives, with the exception of that derived from the compound (I, R=H), as also the methyl derivatives are also insoluble in alkalis.

EXPERIMENTAL.

General Method.—Molecular proportions of the thiosemicarbazide and ethyl monochloroacetate were dissolved in alcohol (dilute, in the case of unsubstituted thiosemicarbazide) and heated under reflux on a water-bath for about an hour. The crystalline condensation product separated out during the progress of the reaction. The mother-liquor usually gave on standing overnight or on further heating a second crop. The substance was purified by crystallisation from suitable solvents.

Acetylation.—The acetylation was carried out by boiling the compounds with an excess of acetic anhydride and a drop of pyridine for 15–20 minutes.

Methylation.—A mixture of the hydroxythiodiazine (1 mol.), methyl iodide (little more than 1 mol.) and methyl alcoholic potassium hydroxide (1 mol.) solution (1 per cent.) was boiled under reflux for 6–7 hours on the water-bath. The contents were then filtered and the brown filtrate evaporated to dryness at the room temperature, when a solid residue was usually obtained. This was collected, dried over porous plate to remove some adhering oil and crystallised.

2-Amino-5-hydroxy-1:3:4-thiodiazine.—It was obtained from ethyl monochloroacetate (or the acid) and thiosemicarbazide in about 70 per cent. yield. The product was extracted with boiling water to remove unaltered thiosemicarbazide and finally crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and pyridine in colourless prisms. It is easily soluble in acetone and pyridine but only sparingly in alcohol. It decomposes and melts at 284°. (Found: N, 32.17. $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{ON}_3\text{S}$ requires N, 32.06 per cent.)

This substance is probably identical with that obtained by Harries and Klamt (*Ber.*, 1900, 33, 1152) from hydrazine and thiocyanacetic acid.

The *acetyl* derivative separates from alcohol as needleshaped crystals melting at 205°. (Found: N, 24·21. $C_5H_7O_2N_3S$ requires N, 24·18 per cent.)

The *benzoyl* derivative, obtained in the usual manner, crystallised from alcohol and melted at 260°. (Found: N, 17·59. $C_{10}H_9O_2N_3S$ requires N, 17·87 per cent.)

2-Amino-5-hydroxy-1:3:4-thiodiazine, like primary amines in general, formed an *additive* compound with phenylthiocarbimide. It separated from alcohol as light yellow needles, m.p. 195°. (Found: N, 20·85. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_4S_2$ requires N, 21·05 per cent.)

2-Methylamino-5-hydroxy-1:3:4-thiodiazine (I, R=Me).—It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, moderately in benzene, and easily in pyridine and acetic acid. It separated as colourless needles from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol; m.p. 282° with decomp. (Found: C, 32·95; H, 5·0; N, 29·08. $C_4H_7ON_3S$ requires C, 33·10; H, 4·83; N, 28·96 per cent.)

The *acetyl* derivative formed pale yellow needles, m.p. 198°. (Found: N, 22·40. $C_6H_9O_2N_3S$ requires N, 22·46 per cent.)

The *methyl* derivative, which was a brown oil, could not be obtained in a sufficiently pure condition.

2-Ethylamino-5-hydroxy-1:3:4-thiodiazine (I, R=Et).—2·5 G. of the product were obtained from 2·9 g. of ethylthiosemicarbazide and 3 g. of ethyl monochloracetate. It separated from acetic acid in colourless prisms melting at 225°. It is very soluble in pyridine but only sparingly in alcohol. (Found: C, 37·58; H, 5·49; N, 26·61. $C_5H_9ON_3S$ requires C, 37·70; H, 5·66; N, 26·41 per cent.)

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised in needles (alcohol) and melted at 169°. (Found: N, 20·80. $C_7H_{11}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 20·89 per cent.)

2-isoButylamino-5-hydroxy-1:3:4-thiodiazine (I, R=isobutyl).—7·2 G. of isobutylthiosemicarbazide and 6 g. of ethyl monochloracetate gave 4·3 g. of pure product. It is sparingly soluble in methyl or ethyl alcohol but moderately in pyridine, acetone, acetic acid and almost insoluble in benzene; m.p. 210°. (Found: N, 22·50. $C_7H_{13}ON_3S$ requires N, 22·46 per cent.)

The *acetyl* derivative formed light yellow needles from absolute alcohol; m.p. 199°. (Found: N, 18·27. $C_9H_{15}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 18·34 per cent.)

The *monomethyl* derivative separated as colourless needles from alcohol, m.p. 135°. It is easily soluble in acetone, sparingly in benzene and insoluble in chloroform. (Found: N, 21.09. $C_8H_{15}ON_3S$ requires N, 20.89 per cent.)

2-Phenylamino-5-hydroxy-1:3:4-thiodiazine (I, R=Ph).—The product, obtained in about 50 per cent. yield, was found to be very sparingly soluble in alcohol, and hot benzene but easily in pyridine, and acetic acid. It separated from the last named solvent as colourless needles, m.p. 184°. (Found: C, 51.9; H, 4.4; N, 20.18. $C_9H_9ON_3S$ requires C, 52.10, H, 4.3; N, 20.3 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative, a pale yellow crystalline compound, crystallised from alcohol and melted at 172°. (Found: N, 16.77. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 16.87 per cent.).

The *methyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. at 265°. (Found: N, 19.19. $C_{10}H_{11}ON_3S$ requires N, 19.00 per cent.).

2-o-Tolylamino-5-hydroxy-1:3:4-thiodiazine (I, R=o-tolyl).—It crystallised from pyridine in colourless needles, m.p. 183°. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol and benzene. (Found: N, 19.12. $C_{10}H_{11}ON_3S$ requires N, 19.00 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative formed light yellow needles, m.p. 210°. (Found: N, 15.90. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 15.96 per cent.).

2-p-Tolylamino-5-hydroxy-1:3:4-thiodiazine (I, R=p-tolyl).—The substance was sparingly soluble in alcohol, benzene or acetone but easily in pyridine and acetic acid. It melted at 195° after crystallisation from pyridine. (Found: N, 18.91. $C_{10}H_{11}ON_3S$ requires N, 19.00 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised in pale yellow needles, m.p. 218°. (Found: N, 16.00. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 15.96 per cent.).